

Maxillary Expansion – A Review Article

Paridhi Jha¹, Vaibhav Misra², Divya Joshi³

Received on: 17 October 2024; Accepted on: 11 January 2025; Published on : 19 February 2025

PG Student¹
Department of Orthodontics
D.J. College of
Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar, Uttar Pradesh

Professor & Head²
Department of Orthodontics
D.J. College of
Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar, Uttar Pradesh

Reader³
Department of Orthodontics
D.J. College of
Dental Sciences & Research
Modinagar, Uttar Pradesh

Abstract

Maxillary expansion is an orthodontic procedure designed to increase the transverse width of the maxilla, addressing skeletal or dental discrepancies such as posterior crossbites, narrow palates, or airway obstruction. The procedure can be performed using appliances like rapid maxillary expanders (RME), slow maxillary expanders (SME), or surgically assisted techniques (SARPE) in skeletally mature patients. This treatment facilitates improved occlusion, enhanced nasal airflow, and better facial aesthetics. Advances in technology, including 3D imaging and CAD/CAM appliances, have optimized treatment planning and outcomes. This article reviews the indications, mechanisms, and outcomes of maxillary expansion, emphasizing its role in comprehensive orthodontic and craniofacial therapy.

Keywords : Maxillary expansion, rapid maxillary expansion, slow maxillary expansion, surgically assisted maxillary expansion.

Introduction

For over a century, maxillary transverse deficit has been corrected with maxillary expansion therapies. E.C. Angell's study, which was published in *Dental Cosmos* in 1860, is the first often quoted report.¹

Although the method was rejected at the time, it is now widely acknowledged as a rather straightforward and reliable orthodontic treatment.

The palate must typically be expanded using a mix of orthodontic and orthopaedic tooth motions in order to correct the transverse disparity. Today, there are three methods of treating maxillary expansion: surgically aided maxillary expansion, slow maxillary expansion (SME), and rapid maxillary expansion (RME). The use of each therapeutic approach is controversial because they each have benefits and drawbacks. Based on their individual experiences, the patient's age, and their malocclusion, practitioners choose therapy appliances.^{2,3}

By the ages of 6 and 9, normal palatal growth is almost finished, and after puberty, separation becomes more challenging due to growing suture interdigitation. 10 to 15 Transverse stresses tip the buccal segments laterally⁴ during treatment, and third-order

moments will cause body translation if the application is designed correctly.⁴

The maxillary suture separates if the force is high enough. Crossbites, distal molar movement, functional appliance treatment, surgical cases (such as bone grafts or arch coordination) to support maxillary protraction, and mild crowding are clinical symptoms that indicate maxillary expansion.⁵

Rapid Maxillary Expansion

Emerson Angell initially described rapid maxillary growth in 1860¹, and Haas later popularized the idea.⁵ RME's primary goal is to narrow the maxillary arch, but because it affects ten bones in the face and head, its effects extend beyond the maxilla.⁶ Rapid maxillary expansion proponents contend that it causes maximum skeletal mobility and minimal dental movement, or tipping.⁷

There is insufficient time for tooth movement to occur when strong, quick forces are applied to the rear teeth, and the forces are then transmitted to the sutures. The

Access this article online

Website : www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code

How to cite this article : Jha et al. - Maxillary Expansion :
A Review Article
HTAJOCD 2025

sutures open up and the teeth move very little in relation to their supporting bone when the force applied by the appliance beyond the threshold required for orthodontic tooth movement and sutural resistance. The midpalatal suture and the other maxillary sutures eventually open as a result of the appliance's compression of the periodontal ligament, bending of the alveolar process, and tipping of the anchor teeth.⁵

Effect of RME on Maxillary and Mandibular Complex

Maxillary skeletal effect : Inoue discovered that the midpalatine suture's aperture was nonparallel and triangular when seen occlusally. It was largest in the incisor area and progressively shrank toward the back of the palate.

The maxillary suture splits superoinferiorly in a nonparallel fashion when seen frontally. It has a pyramidal form, with the base of the pyramid situated on the bone's oral side.⁸

Maxillary halves: Haas⁹ and Wertz¹⁰ found the maxilla to be frequently displaced downward and forward.

Alveolar process: Early in RME, the alveolar processes flex laterally because to the resilience of bone, but this reverts within a few days.¹¹

Maxillary anterior teeth : From the perspective of the patient, the opening of a diastema between the maxillary central incisors is one of the most striking alterations that come with RME. Although the amount of separation between the central incisors should not be interpreted as a measure of the amount of suture separation, it is estimated that during active suture opening, the incisors separate by about half the distance the expansion screw has been opened.¹⁰

Maxillary posterior teeth : The maxillary molars extend and have buccal tipping.

Because to the resistance created by the pterygoid plates and zygomatic buttress, the posterior maxilla extends less easily.

Mandibular effect of RME : The mandible has a propensity to swing backward and downward concurrently.¹²

RME and nasal airflow: Anatomically, the nasal cavity widens immediately after expansion, which facilitates better breathing. Although it may be as big as 8 to 10 mm, the nasal cavity width increase typically averages 1.9 mm.¹³

Indications/Contraindications of RME

When the maxillary molars are already buccally inclined to adjust for the transverse skeletal disparity and the transverse discrepancy is equivalent to or more than 4 mm, rapid maxillary growth is recommended. Patients with cleft lip and palate who have collapsed maxillae are also candidates for rapid palatal expansion (RME), which has been utilized to promote maxillary protraction in class III therapy by interfering with the suture system that connects the maxilla to the cranial base. Lastly, some medical professionals employ the technique to help patients with mild maxillary crowding by lengthening their arches. Patients who have had growth spurt regression, anterior open bite, convex profiles, steep mandibular plane, recession on the buccal face of the molars, and poor compliance should not use it.⁵

Rapid palatal expanders have several drawbacks, such as pain from the high force used, traumatic separation of the midpalatal suture, difficulty correcting rotated molars, needing patient or parent cooperation to activate the appliance, bite

opening, relapse, microtrauma of the midpalatal suture and temporomandibular joint, root resorption, tissue impingement, pain, and a labor-intensive fabrication process.⁵

Clinical Management of RME

During the growth period, the patient or parent should be made aware of the upper midline diastema beforehand.

During the retention period, this is probably going to shut on its own. Twice daily (am and pm), patients should be told to turn the expansion screw a quarter turn. There can be some slight discomfort connected to this. Force levels can reach 10 kg after several turns and tend to build up over several turns. To make sure the midpalatal suture has split, some physicians advise taking an upper occlusal radiograph one week into therapy and reviewing patients every week. There is a danger of alveolar fracture and/or periodontal injury, thus it is crucial to discontinue appliance activation if there is no sign of this. In order to allow for the bone infilling of the split suture, active therapy is often needed for two to three weeks, followed by a three-month retention period.¹⁴

Appliances In RME

These appliances are bonded and banded. The maxillary first molar and first premolar teeth have bands that secure the banded device to them. Because there is no palatal covering, the banded appliances are sanitary. There are two kinds of banded RME:

1. Tissue and tooth-borne
2. A tooth-borne

Tooth Borne RME

1. Hyrax Expander

They consist of only bands and wires without any acrylic covering.

William Biederman first presented the Hyrax expander, a tooth-borne device, in 1968. This kind of device uses a unique screw known as Hyrax, or Hygenic Rapid Expander. In essence, the Hyrax Expander is an all-wire jackscrew that is not spring loaded.¹² The screws' thick gauge wire extensions are soldered to the premolar and molar bands and are designed to fit the palatal curves. This expander's primary benefits are its ease of cleaning and lack of irritation to the palatal mucosa. In a very little amount of use, it may provide sutural separation of 11 mm, and a maximum of 13 mm can also be accomplished. Each activation of the screw produces approximately 0.2 mm of lateral expansion and it is activated from front to back.

2. Issacson Expander

With no palatal covering, it is a tooth-borne device. This expander uses a spring-loaded screw known as the Minne expander, which was created by the University of Minnesota's

dentistry school and is soldered straight to the bands of molars and first premolars.¹² The Minne expander is a precisely calibrated coil spring that is compressed by rotating a nut. The bands on the abutment teeth are soldered to two metal flanges that are perpendicular to the coil. Unless they are partially disengaged, the Minne expander may still apply expansion pressures after the expansion phase is over.

Tooth And Tissue Borne RME

They are made up of acrylic that abuts alveolar ridges and an expansion screw. The following benefits of tooth and tissue RME were listed by Haas in 1970:

- Produces more parallel expansion
- Less relapse
- Greater nasal cavity and apical base gain
- More favorable relationship of the denture bases in width and frequently in the anteroposterior plane as well
- Creates more mobility of the maxilla instead of teeth.

Disadvantage of Tooth and Tissue Borne RME

These tooth and tissue borne RME tend to have higher soft tissue irritation.

Types of Tooth and Tissue Borne RME

1. Haas: The fast expansion procedure's foundation is the destruction of the sutural connective tissue, which results in instantaneous midpalatal suture separation. According to Haas, the quick palatal expander is a stiff device made for maximal dental anchoring that creates expansion in 10–14 days using a jackscrew.⁹

According to him, this will optimize the orthopedic effects, and reports of the forces this equipment produces range from three to ten pounds.

2. **Derichsweiler** : Both the molars and the first premolar have bands.

These bands are soldered to wire tags, which are subsequently put into the screw-containing split palatal acrylic.

Bonded Rapid Palatal Expander

Cohen and Silverman originally described the Bonded RPE in 1973. Except for how it is attached to the teeth, it is comparable to the banded version.

The acrylic covering that covers the posterior parts of this device is attached straight to the teeth.

The bonded appliance has become increasingly popular because of its advantages:

1. It can be easily cemented during the mixed dentition stage, when retention from other appliances can be poor.
2. Number of appointments are reduced.
3. There is reduced posterior teeth tipping and extrusion. The buccal capping limits molar extrusion during treatment and, therefore improves the vertical control, which is particularly useful in class II conditions, as molar extrusion would cause autorotation of the mandible backward and downward resulting in increase in facial convexity and the vertical dimension of the lower face.
4. It provides Bite block effect to facilitate the correction of anterior crossbite.⁵

IPC Rapid Palatal Expander

IPC is intended for both labial alignment of the incisors and orthopedic expansion. The NiTi open coil spring force delivered to the anterior teeth's lingual surface is managed by the IPC while expansion takes place. The midline diastema that frequently happens after RPE treatment is limited by a wire around the distal end of the lateral incisors.⁵

Slow Maxillary Expansion

SME procedures produce less tissue resistance around the circummaxillary structures and, therefore improve bone formation in the intermaxillary suture, which theoretically should eliminate or reduce the limitations of RME.

Slow maxillary expansion involves the use of relatively lesser forces over long time period.

Results are more stable when the maxillary arch is expanded at the rate of 0.5 to 1mm per week.

It delivers a constant physiologic force until the required expansion is obtained

Indications of SME

- Unilateral or bilateral crossbites.
- To correct minimal crowding by gaining space.
- To correct dental crossbite in permanent dentition.
- To correct mild maxillary deficiency in cleft lip and palate patients by providing slow continuous forces.

Contraindications of SME

- Adult patients who have completed their growth.

Appliances In SME

Coffin Appliance

Given by Walter Coffin–1875. It is a removable appliance capable of slow dento alveolar expansion. The appliance consists of an omega-shaped wire of 1.25 mm thickness, placed in the midpalatal region. The free ends of the omega wire are embedded in acrylic covering the slopes of the palate. The spring is activated by pulling two asides apart manually.

Magnets

Repulsive magnetic forces for maxillary expansion were first described by Vardemon et al 1987.¹⁵

In contrast to general expansion effects, banded magnets caused more noticeable skeletal effects. A constant 250–500 g strain may cause skeletal and dental motions, to varying degrees depending on the patient's condition (growth, age, etc.). Due to the possibility of corrosive compounds forming, magnets have a tendency to oxidize in the oral environment. However, this may be avoided by covering the magnets. These magnets have the benefit of imparting measurable constant force over an extended period of time, which reduces the chance of external root resorption. Because they need to be well stabilized and have strong guide rods to keep the magnets from going out of line and producing undesired rotational motions, these magnets are rather large.

W-Arch

Ricketts and his associates¹⁶ first employed the "W" expansion device to treat individuals with cleft palates (Fig. 6). Made of 36 mm steel wire soldered two molar bands, the

W-arch is a permanent prosthetic. The lingual arch should be built to rest 1-1.5 mm off the palatal soft tissue in order to prevent irritation of the soft tissue. It may be readily modified to allow more anterior than posterior expansion, or vice versa, if desired. It is triggered by simply opening the apices of the W-arch. Before being inserted, the appliance should be set to the right force levels, which are delivered when it is opened 3–4 mm wider than the passive width.

Up to the cross bite, expansion should continue at a rate of 2 mm each month.

Quadhelix

Ricketts described the quadhelix appliance, which is a variation of Coffin's W-spring (Fig. 7). The W-spring's flexibility and activation range were improved with the addition of four helices. Depending on which teeth arch in a crossbite, the appliance's palatal arms might have different lengths. More recently, a new generation of prefabricated appliances made of nickel titanium have been released. Using nickel titanium provides several benefits over stainless steel, including better force delivery due to its superelastic qualities. This might result in more fast crossbite correction and greater physiological tooth movement.

Mode of Action

In prepubertal youngsters, the quadhelix appliance functions by combining skeletal growth with buccal tipping in a 6:1 ratio.

Clinical Management

By activating the appliance by 8 mm, or roughly one molar width, the desired force level of 400 gm may be provided. Every six weeks, patients should be reassessed.³ The device may occasionally leave an impression on the tongue, but this will quickly go away after treatment. Continue expanding until the buccal cusps of the mandibular molars and the palatal cusps of the upper molars meet edge-to-edge. Since relapse is unavoidable, some overcorrection is preferable. After expansion is accomplished, a three-month retention period with the quadhelix in place is advised. After the stainless steel wires are installed, the quadhelix can be taken off if fixed appliances are being utilized.

Benefits include : cost-effectiveness, non-compliance, molar rotation/torque, orthopaedic impact, differential expansion, habit breaker, good retention, and a wide spectrum of action.

Drawbacks include : restricted skeletal change, bite opening, and molar tilting.

Spring Jet

Soldering or attaching the spring jet's active components to the molar bands is done (Fig. 8). To ensure that the forces

pass near the maxillary teeth's center of resistance, the telescoping unit is positioned up to 5 mm from the center of the molar tubes; nevertheless, it should be 1.5 mm from the palatal tissue.

The permanent dentition receives 400 gm of force, while the mixed dentition receives 240 gm. The lock screw must be moved horizontally along the telescopic tube to activate. The spring can be squeezed thanks to a ball stop on the transpalatal wire.

NiTi Expander

Wendell V17 introduced the Nickel Titanium Palatal Expanders (Fig. 9). It produces consistent, ideal expansion forces. The remainder of the component is composed of stainless steel, while the core is composed of a thermally activated NiTi alloy. With just an extra lingual sheath on the molar bands, the expander can be utilized in conjunction with traditional fixed appliances.

The shape memory and transition temperature effects of nickel titanium cause the appliance to function.¹⁸ The transition temperature of the nickel titanium component is 94° F. The expander is too rigid to bend for insertion at room temperature. The expander's primary component becomes softer when chilled, making handling simpler. It stiffens and starts to regain its former shape after placement. A 3 mm increment of expansion exerts only about 350 gm of force. A 31 and the nickel titanium alloy provides relatively uniform force levels as the expander deactivates.

Surgical Techniques

As people age, the impact of the dental arch on the maxillary base decreases, thus medically aided expansion procedures may be an option. The following are signs of surgical expansion:

1. To make the arch wider
2. When a significant degree of expansion (>7 mm) is necessary to rectify a posterior crossbite and prevent the possible elevated risk of segmental osteotomies.
3. In situations when there is extensive buccal gingival recession

in the canine-bicuspid area of the maxilla, highly thin and fragile gingival tissue, or severe nasal stenosis, the arch should be widened after maxillary collapse linked to a cleft palate.

Among the methods are

- Rapid palatal expansion with surgical assistance (SARPE)¹⁹
- Maxillary segmental surgery

Surgically aided rapid palatal expansion, or SARPE, has become more and more well-liked as a means of treating maxillary transverse deficiency (MTD). It enables medical professionals to effectively expand the maxilla in a patient with a mature skeleton.

Segmental Maxillary Surgery : By making an extra surgical incision along the midpalatal suture, a Le Fort I osteotomy might result in transverse extension.

After that, the maxillary halves are split apart and held in their new place. The amount of expansion that may be accomplished is restricted by the palatal mucoperiosteum's relative inelasticity.

In order to ease surgical access to the osteotomy site, orthodontic therapy entails separating the maxillary central incisor roots prior to surgery. When a patient needs expansion and has concurrent sagittal and/or vertical maxillary inconsistencies, this is the preferred method.

Conclusion

There are several methods for achieving maxillary dentition and maxilla expansion. The choice of expansion is heavily influenced by the skeletal and dental patterns, and the expansion type can significantly support the overall goals of therapy.

Bibliography

1. Timms DJ. The dawn of rapid maxillary expansion. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 1999 Jun 1;69(3):247-50.
2. Ficarelli JP. A brief review of maxillary expansion. *The Journal of pedodontics*. 1978;3(1):29-35.
3. Bell RA. A review of maxillary expansion in relation to rate of expansion and patient's age. *American journal of orthodontics*. 1982 Jan 1;81(1):32-7.
4. Cleall JF, Bayne DI, Posen JM, Subtelny JD. Expansion of the midpalatal suture in the monkey. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 1965 Jan 1;35(1):23-35.
5. Agarwal A, Mathur R. Maxillary expansion. *International journal of clinical pediatric dentistry*. 2010 Sep;3(3):139.
6. Ceylan İ, Oktay H, Demirci M. The effect of rapid maxillary expansion on conductive hearing loss. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 1996 Aug 1;66(4):301-8.
7. Bell RA. A review of maxillary expansion in relation to rate of expansion and patient's age. *American journal of orthodontics*. 1982 Jan 1;81(1):32-7.
8. Bishara SE, Staley RN. Maxillary expansion: Clinical implication. *Am*

- J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop 1987 Jan;91(1):3-14.
9. Haas AJ. Rapid expansion of the maxillary dental arch and nasal cavity by opening the midpalatal suture. *Angle Orthod* 1961;31: 73-90.
 10. Wertz RA. Skeletal and dental changes accompanying rapid midpalatal suture opening. *Am J Orthod* 1970 Jul;58(1):41-66.
 11. Isaacson RJ, Wood JL, Ingram AH. Forces produced by rapid maxillary expansion. I. Design of the force measuring system. *Angle Orthod* 1964;34:256-260.
 12. Bishara SE, Staley RN. Maxillary expansion: Clinical implication. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop* 1987 Jan;91(1):3-14.
 13. Gray LP. Results of 310 cases of rapid maxillary expansion selected for medical reasons. *J Laryngol Otol* 1975 Jun;89(6):601-614.
 14. Gill D, Naini F, McNally M, Jones A. The management of transverse maxillary deficiency. *Dent Update* 2004 Nov;31(9): 516-523.
 15. Vardimon AD, Graber TM, Voss LR, Verrusio E. Magnetic versus mechanical expansion with different force thresholds and points of force application. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop* 1987 Dec;92(6):455-466.
 16. Ricketts, RM.; Bench, RW.; Gungino, CF., et al Bioprogressive therapy. *Rocky Mountain/ Orthodontics*; 1979. p. 255-258
 17. Arndt WV. Nickel titanium palatal expander. *J Clin Orthod* 1993 Mar;27(3):129-137.
 18. Marzban R, Nanda R. Slow maxillary expansion with nickel titanium. *J Clin Orthod* 1999 Aug;33(8):431-441.
 19. Suri L, Taneja P. Surgically assisted rapid palatal expansion: a literature review. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop* 2008 Feb;133(2):290-302.